
LANGUAGE PECULIARITIES OF JOURNALISTIC STYLE

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Abstract: The article deals with the problem of publicistic style to be exact about language peculiarities of journalistic style. The journalistic style is characterized by the combination of contrasting stylistic coloring of words: it uses book vocabulary and colloquial, in high and low level. As a result of the analysis of articles from well-known periodical publications British presses "The Daily Telegraph", "The Guardian", "The Independent", "Daily Mirror", "The Sun", "Daily Mail", "Daily Express" the common features of the journal language have been identified.

Key words: media. Journalistic article, language, style.

At present the study of the specifics of the language of the media is today one of the most important tasks, since the development of technical software, especially computer innovation, is accompanied by enormous increase in the amount of information. For a society with expansion international relations, with the improvement of methods and techniques of spreading of the media is increasingly important in life acquire various types of mass communication. The media presents to the attention of the public specially selected and well organized materials. The subject of this new discipline is the study of the functioning of language in public communication. The most studied media language is the language of the magazine, which is the most widespread in the mass communication. Glossy publications today represent a special kind and take their place in the modern media system.

The purpose of this work is to analyze language peculiarities of journalistic style especially of glossy paper journals. From the Latin language we know the verb *publicare* - "to make common property, open to all" or "explain publicly, make public". It is from the term journalism originated. Publicity is a special type of literary works that highlight, explain topical issues of social and political life are raised moral issues The events of our time have found their reflection in different genres: informational (note, reporting, report, interview, chronicle, review), analytical (article, correspondence, commentary, review, review), artistic and journalistic (essay, feuilleton, pamphlet)

The journalistic style is characterized by the combination of contrasting stylistic coloring of words: it uses book vocabulary and colloquial, in high and low level. The

usage of diverse vocabulary and phraseology depends on the genre and should be subject to the principle aesthetic expediency. If, for example, in a feuilleton it is possible to use vernacular, mixing styles to achieve comic sound, then in information genres such a variety of language means are not justified. The areas of application of journalism are subdivided into newspaper, journalism, radio and television journalism; the modern world represents new branch – internet journalism. Each of these branches has its own speech features. The most well studied is journalism, its genres and specificity.

Journalistic text is quite possible to call a traditional means of mass information and propaganda. According to I.R. Galperin, “journalistic text is a product of a speech-creating process that has completed in the form of a journal article” [2, 19].

The journalistic text, like the journal itself, performs two main functions: informative and influencing (volitional). There are three types of journalistic text: informative, characteristic for taking notes, records, reports, messages; analytical, used in current articles, comments, reviews; artistic- journalistic, for essays, pamphlets, reports, feuilletons [1,196]. English-language magazines are characterized with well developed system of terminology on social and political topics.

As a result of the analysis of articles from well-known periodical publications

British presses The Daily Telegraph, The Guardian, The Independent", "Daily Mirror", "The Sun", "Daily Mail", "Daily Express" the following common features of the journal language have been identified:

nouns in the function of modifier: "a picture-perfect family life" (ideal family life); [3]

the use of neologisms: "shrinkflation"(Brexit) (Шринкфляция) [4],

«Brexit» (Брекзит) [5];

omitted qualifying words, auxiliary verbs, articles: Christopher Snowdon, head of lifestyle economics at the Institute of Economics Affairs, said..." (Christopher lifestyle at the Institute of Economics) [6].

One of the favorite ways of the Britain press can be considered using:

Abbreviations: "OPCC", "EU", "MPs", "UK-EU", "CJEU", "SNP".

Analysis of the articles demonstrated presence of such group of grammatic phenomena, as: compound subject:

«Meghan Markle’s sister-in-law is said to have been doubting her boy friend when she learned he was going clubbing with his friends instead of seeing her»[3]

Aytiwlarg’a qarag’anda, Meghan Markldin’ jen’gesi dostinin’ onin’ menen ushirasiw ornina doslari menen klubqa ketkenin bilgennen, og’an gu’man menen qaradi»

compound object: «Health bosses battling the obesity crisis, want kids to consume 20 percent less sugar by 2020»[4] -“Semizlik krizisine qarsi guresip atirg’an den sawliqti saqlaw basshilari, balalar 2020 jilga kelip 20% kemirek qantti qollaniwin qaleydi”.

Infinitive in the function of the predicate: «Very little is actually about execution, because the execution's primary purpose is to represent the idea»[7]

According to the analysis carried out, it can be confirmed that English-speaking journal articles contain a large number of proposals written in direct speech:

«According to the book's author Jessica Jayne: «Kate was further humiliated when a photo of William with two girls was published in tabloids» - Kitaptin' avtorı Jesika Jeinnin' aytqanınday: ' "Uilyamnın' eki qız benen suwreti tabloidlarda jariyalang'anda Keyt ja'nede kemsitildi ha'm ezildi«

In addition, the words of political vocabulary are often used: «officials» (chinovnikler), «summit» (саммит), «negotiations» (so'ylesiwler), «spokesman» (so'ylewshi) [5].

Impossible to present British journal without using of verbs in the passive voice: «It's a series of copies and each copy is done by people other than myself, from the sculpture that precedes it in the chain»

Metaphor is one of the brightest phenomena in language of Britain journals: «...and then lashed out with both gargantuan paws»[8].

For practical work, the most essential are the following characteristic features of the English press:

- 1 Colloquial and familiar nature of a number of materials;
- 2 "Decorating" the style with the use of jargon, periphrases and the like;
3. Officiality of titles and appeals;
4. A special characteristic of journal headlines;
5. A special way to highlight paragraphs;
6. Lexical features of journal-informational materials;
7. Use of terms.

Let's look at each of these traits in more detail.

1. The use of colloquial turns, even in the most serious the content of the text. For example, the English magazine "Daily Worker" writes.

One admission by Herr Strauss was accidental. Pressed into a corner about whether it wasn't time to have a new de-Nazification in his Ministry? He ran round the question. Instead of answering he took the line of "you're another", that other West German Ministries and the police had still more ex-nazis in them than his own Ministry [2].

We noted earlier that it may be unusual for the reader that the familiarity with which the English and American press treats statesmen, both domestic and foreign. Often heads of state and ministers are referred to in the magazine by their names: Bob Kennedy (Robert Kennedy), their surnames are familiarly abbreviated: Mac (Macmillan) and the like.

Use of names and titles in the magazine-information style makes the message specific and relates the information being conveyed to certain persons, institutions or areas. The author must imply significant prior (background) knowledge of the Receptor, allowing it to associate the name with the specified object. So, English receptor out of context knows that Park Lane is a street, Piccadilly Circus is - an area of circus, Columbia Pictures is a movie company, LA is a commonly used abbreviation for Los Angeles.

In conclusion we may confirm that Mass media is an integral part of modern life and one of the keys to the successful functioning of society. Journalistic style, in particular, the style of journal articles, occupies a place in this system of paramount importance with the growing popularity of glossy publications on throughout the development of this phenomenon of printed periodicals until today.

The task of the media is to provide special materials that are designed to provide a number of functions, including informative and stimulating, and this is one of the main features, in particular, the style of glossy magazines.

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